

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part II: Campylobacteriosis

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 71 primary studies investigating only sporadic campylobacteriosis, which were conducted between 1981 and 2012. From these, nineteen studies investigated exposures in children and infants, while only two studies focused on the susceptible (elderly and immunocompromised) population. These primary studies provided 1326 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 72% of the meta-analytical data produced by case-control studies from UK (14), USA (12), Australia (6), Norway (4) and Denmark (4). Forty case-control studies (56%) employed a matched design and produced a total of 869 matched ORs. Six-hundred and seventy-three reported ORs were not adjusted by any confounder, while 653 ORs were adjusted by using either Mantel-Haenzel method or logistic regressions. Conditional logistic, either in univariate or multivariate analysis, was the most widely used model, producing 550 OR measures, while the simplest univariate-mode chi-square was the most unfrequently used, rendering only 192 ORs. After methodological quality assessment, 18 case-control studies were marked as being below standards, which yielded a total of 86 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of exposure (1229 ORs) than on host specific factors (69) and travel (28).

According to this meta-analysis study, the most important determinants of disease in the children population, in decreasing order are: contaminated or untreated drinking water (overall OR=4.93; 95% CI: 2.82 – 8.62), consumption of raw-egg containing products (overall OR=4.85; 95% CI: 2.99 – 7.85), exposure to recreational water (overall OR=4.68; 95% CI: 2.63 – 8.32), exposure to farm/rural environment (overall OR=4.43; 95% CI: 2.57 – 7.63), person-to-person contagion (overall OR=4.22; 95% CI: 2.21 – 8.05), consumption of raw milk (overall OR=3.05; 95% CI: 1.93 – 4.84), pork (overall OR=2.34; 95% CI: 1.36 – 4.03), other meats (overall OR=2.29; 95% CI: 1.58 – 3.32), minced beef (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.22 – 4.24), exposure through playground (overall OR=2.20; 95% CI: 1.34 – 3.61),

processed meats (overall OR=2.18; 95% CI: 1.25 – 3.80), any composite food mostly eaten out (overall OR=2.16; 95% CI: 1.08 – 4.34) and poultry (overall OR=2.08; 95% CI: 1.38 – 3.13).

In the mixed population, as a whole, host-specific factors and environmental/animal routes (pooled ORs from 2.06 – 3.48), bear discernibly greater risk of transmission of campylobacteriosis than food consumption (pooled ORs from 0.75 to 1.78) with only two exceptions (raw milk at an OR of 2.64; and other meats comprising meat fondue, BBQ, grilled meat and offal at an OR of 2.21). The most important determinants of disease in the mixed population are: handling of manure (overall OR=3.48; 95% CI: 1.92 – 6.31), international travel (overall OR=3.05; 95% CI: 2.09 – 4.45), occupational exposure to animals/carcasses/meat (overall OR=2.96; 95% CI: 2.30 – 3.80), recent use of anti-acids (overall OR=2.91; 95% CI: 2.10 – 4.05), contact with farm animals (overall OR=2.44; 95% CI: 2.01 – 2.97), attendance to day care (overall OR=2.39; 95% CI: 1.45 – 3.94), exposure to recreational water (overall OR=2.37; 95% CI: 1.57 – 3.57), exposure to farm/rural environment (overall OR=2.34; 95% CI: 1.60 – 3.42), exposure to wild animals (overall OR=2.33; 95% CI: 1.56 – 3.45), contaminated drinking water (overall OR=2.26; 95% CI: 1.57 – 3.27), suffering from any chronic disease (overall OR=2.22; 95% CI: 1.54 – 3.21) and being under other medications or medical treatment (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 1.36 – 3.11).

Within the food vehicles of transmission, the highest associations with campylobacteriosis were observed for: raw milk (overall OR=2.64; 95% CI: 1.74 – 4.01), other meats (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.90 – 2.57), poultry (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 1.54 – 2.05), raw milk's cheese (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 0.97 – 3.06), BBQ meats (overall OR=1.67; 95% CI: 1.26 – 2.21), fast-food composite (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 1.35 – 1.87), raw seafood (overall OR=1.50; 95% CI: 1.05 – 2.14), eggs (overall OR=1.45; 95% CI: 1.09 – 1.95), beef (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 1.22 – 1.68) and bottled water (overall OR=1.39; 95% CI: 1.23 – 1.58). Foodstuffs that on meta-analysis had weak or non-significant association with campylobacteriosis were: vegetables, fruits, molluscs, sprouts, dairy-based RTE, fungi and spices, fish, alcoholic beverages and processed fish.

Other meta-analysis models were adjusted to estimate the effects of food handling (raw and undercooked) and setting (home, eating out) on the mean ORs in selected food classes. It was found that people who ate undercooked chicken had 2.236 (95% CI: 1.887 – 2.648) greater probability of acquiring campylobacteriosis than those who (stated to have) consumed *simply* chicken, which was a pooled OR higher than that of consuming rare beef (overall OR=1.881; 95% CI: 1.328 – 2.664). In general, eating raw foods conveyed an increased risk of disease, particularly for unpasteurised milk and raw milk's cheese (2.420 times higher risk) which was greater than consuming raw eggs (1.892 times higher risk) and raw seafood (1.624 times higher risk). People who ate poultry, beef, processed meats and composite dishes prepared outside home had their odds of infection significantly increased by a factor of 1.251 – 1.850 whereas eating poultry prepared at home seemingly had a protective effect, by reducing the odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis by 1.270 (95% CI: 0.911 – 1.473).

3. Results

3.2 *Campylobacter* spp.

3.2.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors pertaining to the human infection with campylobacteriosis, a total of 1214 bibliographic sources were identified using the keywords in the five search engines, from which only 104 passed the screening for relevance comprising case-control studies from both sporadic illnesses and outbreaks. However, for *Campylobacter*, meta-analysis was undertaken only on sporadic disease. The quality assessment stage was passed by 71 primary studies investigating sporadic campylobacteriosis, which were conducted between 1981 and 2012. These primary studies provided a total of 1326 categorised odds-ratios for meta-analysis. A total of 609 ORs were retrieved from 28 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 717 ORs were excerpted from 43 case-control studies performed after 2000. While the majority of ORs were available for illness caused by any *Campylobacter* species (1032 ORs), fewer ORs were reported for cases caused specifically by *C. jejuni* (25 ORs) or *C. coli* (39 ORs) (Figure 1).

The countries with the highest number of case-control studies for sporadic campylobacteriosis were UK (14), USA (12), Australia (6), Norway (4) and Denmark (4), which produced all together ~72% of the meta-analytical data. Out of 71 studies, nineteen studies investigated pathways of exposure in children and infants, and seven in the adult population, while only two studies focused on the susceptible population. Susceptible populations originated from elderly (Doorduyn et al., 2010) and patients suffering from ulcerative colitis (Arora et al., 2015). This data was so fragmented (only 22 ORs) that no meta-analysis model could be adjusted exclusively for this population type.

Most of the primary studies carried out regular case-control investigations (50) in the mixed population. Because exposures were investigated in the mixed population much more frequently (925 ORs) than in the adult population (176 ORs) (Figure 2), the ORs coming from the “Adult” population were moved to the category “Mixed” for later meta-analysis. However, as a rule, because of their distinct routes of exposure, the children and mixed populations were not assessed in a single meta-analysis model, but in separate meta-analyses. Data from both age groups were combined only when the ORs belonging to the children population were too few to run a separate meta-analysis model.

In seventy primary studies, the campylobacteriosis cases were laboratory-confirmed, while only in one study (Eberhart-Phillips et al., 1997) there was an indication that nearly all of the cases were confirmed. Forty case-control studies (56%) employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 869 categorised ORs. While 145 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis, 724 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated using CL (550) and MH (246) and some of them by UL (27) and the simple chi-square test (46). From the case-control studies that used an unmatched or frequency-matched design (33 studies), 298 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 159 in multivariate analysis. Most of the ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using UL (281) and chi-square (146), whereas only 30 ORs were MH-estimates adjusted by a confounder’s strata. Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 673 extracted ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while 653 ORs were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions. After methodological quality assessment, 18 case-control

studies were marked as being below standards. They provided a total of 86 potentially-biased ORs whose influence on the meta-analysed OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook's distance. Whenever they were determined to be influential, they were removed from the meta-analysis models. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations concentrated more on the multiple pathways of transmission (1229 ORs) than on host specific factors (69) and travel (28) (Figure 2). General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 2 by case-control study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio and potential for bias status.

Figure 1. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control studies of sporadic human campylobacteriosis by country (top left), serotype (top right) and population type (bottom)

Figure 2. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control studies of sporadic campylobacteriosis by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), risk factor (bottom left) and assigned potential for bias (bottom right)

Figure 4. Flow chart of literature search for case-control studies of human campylobacteriosis
*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

3.2.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal- and food-related pathways of transmission*

In the meta-analyses, there was a recurrent significant difference in the measured associations between campylobacteriosis and exposures between study periods (before and after the year 2000). In the children population, higher pooled ORs were registered in case-control studies conducted after 2000 for exposures related to animal contact ($p=0.029$; Table 3B), environmental pathways ($p=0.003$; Table 4 B), general food pathways ($p=0.098$; Table 6B), and consumption of beef ($p=0.005$; Table 7B), and dairy products ($p=0.097$; Table 9B). In some of the meta-analyses for the mixed population, there was no noticeable effect of study period on the measured ORs. However, when significant effects were found, opposed to what was observed in the children population, in the mixed population there was a tendency for exposures tested after the year 2000 to bear lower ORs. Pooled OR estimates in the mixed population were found to be lower in recent years for exposures linked to travel ($p=0.004$), animal contact ($p=0.042$; Table 3B), person-to-person contagion ($p=0.012$; Table 5B), and consumption of seafood ($p=0.096$; Table 10B) and BBQ meats ($p=0.143$; Table 15B). Said otherwise, while ORs determined after the year 2000 tended to be higher in children, they tended to be lower in the mixed population. This interaction between population type and study period was not further studied.

Travel was an important source for acquiring campylobacteriosis in all the geographical regions, as denoted by the significant meta-analysed ORs ranging from 2.476 to 5.629 (all with $p<.0001$ in Table 1A). For the general meta-analysis on travel subcategories, no geographical region was removed. For nationals of USA, UK, Switzerland, Ireland, France, Germany, Australia and New Zealand, travelling abroad increased their odds of infection with campylobacteriosis by an average of 3.046 (95% CI: 2.087 – 4.450). Domestic travelling represented a significantly lower risk at an overall OR of 1.458 (95% CI: 0.697 – 3.049), as meta-analysed from nationals of Spain, USA, Greece and the UK (Table 1B). The meta-analysis conducted on the travel data partition implied the probable existence of a file-drawer problem ($p=0.007$). The respective funnel plot hinted that travel exposures with low or non-significant ORs, from small case-control studies, were likely to have remained unpublished (Figure 3). No potentially-biased OR was removed after assessing influential observations by Cook's distance.

Table 1A. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for *Campylobacter* transmission by geographical region for the combined mixed (n=22 ORs) and children (n=5 ORs) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and Children					
North America	1.723	0.333	6	[1.071 – 2.375]	<.0001
North Europe	0.907	0.236	10	[0.443 – 1.371]	<.0001
Oceania	1.728	0.397	4	[0.951 – 2.505]	<.0001
West Europe	1.227	0.261	7	[0.714 – 1.739]	<.0001

Table 1B. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for *Campylobacter* transmission for the combined mixed (n=21 ORs) and children (n=4 ORs) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Travel abroad	1.114 ^b	0.193	21	[0.736 – 1.493]	<.0001
Travel inside	0.377 ^a	0.376	4	[-0.360 – 1.115]	0.316
Before 2000	0.706	0.242		[0.231 – 1.180]	0.004
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0935	QE(df=22)		QM(df=2)	
s^2_{v2} (Abroad)	0.0721	p<.001		p<.001	
s^2_{v1} (Inside)	0.3166				
s^2 (residual)	0.5521				
Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0001			0.007
Points removed	0				

Figure 3. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for *Campylobacter* transmission. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Overall, many medical conditions acted as predisposition factors for campylobacteriosis, particularly in regions of Oceania (overall OR=2.138; p=0.088) and Western Europe (overall OR=2.534; p=0.008; Table 2A). In Northern Europe, the overall association between host-specific factors and campylobacteriosis was notably weaker (overall OR=1.502; p=0.233). In the general meta-analyses for host-specific subcategories, all geographical regions were kept in both the children and the mixed population.

Table 2A. Meta-analyses of host specific factors for *Campylobacter* transmission by region for the mixed population (n=65)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.583	0.488	6	[-0.374 – 1.541]	0.233
North Europe	0.407	0.288	33	[-0.158 – 0.972]	0.158
Oceania	0.760	0.445	7	[-0.113 – 1.633]	0.088
West Europe	0.930	0.350	19	[0.243 – 1.615]	0.008

In the mixed population, chronic conditions such as chronic gastrointestinal illnesses, stomach ulcer, coeliac disease, liver disease, asthma and diabetes (overall OR=2.221; 95% CI: 1.539 – 3.209; Table 2B) were as strong predisposing factors for campylobacteriosis as other medical conditions (overall OR=2.058; 95% CI: 1.362 – 3.108), including stomach surgery, cholecystectomy and the use of ulcer medicines, steroid tablets and other prescription drugs. While the lowest pooled OR was found for the recent use of antibiotics (1.43; 95% CI: 1.001 – 2.063), the highest risk was posed by the recent use of antacids (overall OR=2.912; 95% CI: 2.096 – 4.047). Similarly, in the susceptible population (Table 2B), the use of antacids (overall OR=2.907; 95% CI: 1.202 – 7.063) posed a significantly higher risk of campylobacteriosis than chronic diseases (overall OR=2.108; 95% CI: 0.972 – 4.577). Meta-analysing results from a total of 545 campylobacteriosis cases in children between 0 – 2 years old and 1217 healthy infants from USA, Spain and Algeria, it was estimated that breastfeeding exerts a protective effect, overall reducing the odds of disease by 3.164 (95% CI: 1.154 - 8.620; Table 2B). In both the mixed and the children population data partitions, the publication bias test failed to detect any effect of study size on the measured ORs (p=0.740 and p=0.780, respectively). The corresponding funnel plots are presented in Figure 4.

Table 2B. Meta-analyses of host specific factors for *Campylobacter* transmission for mixed (n=65) and children/susceptible (n=11) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Antiacids	1.069 ^c	0.168	19	[0.740 – 1.398]	<.0001
	Antibiotics	0.362 ^a	0.185	21	[0.001– 0.724]	0.049
	Chronic	0.798 ^b	0.187	12	[0.431 – 1.166]	<.0001
	Other Med	0.722 ^b	0.210	13	[0.309 – 1.134]	0.070
	UniOR	-0.188	0.127		[-0.436 – 0.061]	0.138
	Before 2000					0.255

Random effects						
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2277	QE(df=59)			QM(df=4)	
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0030	p<.001			p<.001	
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0003					
s^2 (residual)	0.6770					
Publication bias	-0.000	-0.000				0.740
Points removed	1					
Suscept /	Fixed effects					
Infants	Antiacids in susceptible	1.067 ^c	0.452	2	[0.184 – 1.955]	0.018
	Breastfed children	-1.151 ^a	0.514	3	[-2.158 - -0.144]	0.025
	Chronic in susceptible	0.746 ^b	0.395	6	[-0.028 – 1.521]	0.059
	Before 2000					ND
Random effects						
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1565	QE(df=6)			QM(df=4)	
s^2 (residual)	0.5803	p=0.010			p<.001	
Publication bias	-0.0007	0.0025				0.780
Points removed	1					

ND. Not determined as all OR measures were from case-control studies conducted after the year 2000

Figure 4. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right)

Contact with animals poses a significant risk of transmission of *Campylobacter* in the four geographical regions: North America (overall OR=1.974; p<.0001), Northern Europe (overall OR=1.726; p<.0001), Oceania (overall OR=1.863; p=0.004) and Western Europe (overall OR=1.452; p=0.046 in Table 3A). Within each of the geographical regions above, children were more susceptible of contagion through animal contact than the mixed population as shown by the higher pooled ORs (2.100 – 2.568; Table 3A). The OR measures belonging to Southamerican children presented a lower meta-analysed value (1.625), and so they were removed for the general meta-analysis by animal-contact subcategory.

Table 3A. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for *Campylobacter*-transmission by region in the mixed (n=229) and children (n=54) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.680	0.163	90	[0.360 – 1.000]	<.0001
North Europe	0.546	0.120	87	[0.311 – 0.782]	<.0001
Oceania	0.622	0.214	28	[0.201 – 1.042]	0.004
West Europe	0.373	0.187	24	[0.007 – 0.739]	0.046
Children					
North America	0.943	0.315	13	[0.325 – 1.560]	0.003
North Europe	0.904	0.518	10	[-0.111 – 1.919]	0.081
Oceania	0.762	0.355	15	[0.066 – 1.459]	0.032
South America	0.486	0.531	3	[-0.554 – 1.527]	0.360
West Europe	0.742	0.308	13	[0.138 – 1.346]	0.016

In the mixed population, the overall odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis from contact with farm animals (OR=2.442; 95% CI: 2.010 – 2.968) is statistically comparable to that from contact with wild animals (OR=2.330; 95% CI: 1.559 – 3.480; Table 3B). While the lowest association with campylobacteriosis was related to contact with pets (overall OR=1.519; 95% CI: 1.279 – 1.802), the highest one (overall OR=2.960; 95% CI: 2.303 – 3.808) was posed by occupational-related routes of transmission, encompassing exposures such as working in a slaughterhouse/farm/petshop/zoo, working in food preparation, and animal husbandry. Children were found to be more susceptible of acquiring campylobacteriosis from animal-contact pathways of exposure than the mixed population (Table 3B): notice that the odds of infection for children who had contact with farm animals (overall OR=4.646; 95% CI: 1.416 – 15.25) and pets at home (overall OR=3.819; 95% CI: 1.157 – 12.604) were higher than those of the mixed population, in the respective categories. Both the funnel plots (Figure 5) and the study-size effect test (Table 3B) implied that there was no evidence of file-drawer problem in any of the meta-analyses, for the mixed and children population.

Table 3B. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for *Campylobacter*-transmission in the mixed (n=229) and children (n=51) population – South America was removed from the children population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Farm	0.893 ^b	0.100	81	[0.698 – 1.088]	<.0001
	Occupational	1.085 ^c	0.128	32	[0.834 – 1.337]	<.0001
	Pets	0.418 ^a	0.088	105	[0.246 – 0.589]	<.0001
	Wild	0.846 ^b	0.205	11	[0.444 – 1.247]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.171	0.085		[-0.336 – -0.005]	0.044
	Before 2000	0.228	0.112		[0.008 – 0.448]	0.042
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0785	QE(df=220)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0003	p<.001		p<.001	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0169				
	s^2 (residual)	0.5078				
	Publication bias	0.000	0.000			0.796
	Points removed	3				
Children	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Farm	1.536 ^b	0.606	21	[0.348 – 2.725]	0.011
	Pets	1.340 ^a	0.609	30	[0.146 – 2.534]	0.028
	UniOR	-0.562	0.548		[-1.636 – 0.513]	0.305
	Before 2000	-0.473	0.217		[-0.898 – -0.048]	0.029
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0513	QE(df=47)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.7347	p=0.012		p=0.023	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0207				
	s^2 (residual)	0.5667				
	Publication bias	0.0003	0.0004			0.449
	Points removed	0				

Figure 5. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of animal contact pathways as risk factors for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analyses on the environmental pathways for *Campylobacter* infection revealed that in North America the pooled risks in the mixed population (OR=2.298) and in the children population (OR=1.966) were slightly higher than those of the other geographical regions (pooled ORs 1.453 – 1.613 and 1.369 – 1.678, respectively; Table 4A). In the mixed population, the associations between *Campylobacter* transmission and environmental sources were all significant, while in the children population pooled ORs were not significant in case-control studies from Eastern Europe, Oceania and Western Europe, most likely due to the very few data points available from those regions (Table 4A). For the meta-analyses by subcategory (Table 4B), information from all regions were kept.

Table 4A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission by region for mixed (n=120) and children (n=31) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.832	0.163	44	[0.513 – 1.151]	<.0001
North Europe	0.374	0.111	61	[0.157 – 0.592]	0.001
Oceania	0.646	0.286	8	[0.085 – 1.207]	0.024
West Europe	0.478	0.227	7	[0.034 – 0.922]	0.035
Children					
East Europe	0.518	0.331	2	[-0.130 – 1.167]	0.117
North America	0.676	0.186	15	[0.312 – 1.041]	<.0001
North Europe	0.507	0.252	6	[0.012 – 1.001]	0.045
Oceania	0.336	0.441	4	[-0.528 – 1.200]	0.446
West Europe	0.314	0.336	4	[-0.344 – 0.972]	0.350

Table 4B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission for mixed (n=120) and children (n=30) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Day care	0.870 ^a	0.255	3	[0.370 – 1.370]	<.0001
	Drink water	0.817 ^a	0.187	66	[0.449 – 1.184]	<.0001
	Farm	0.850 ^a	0.195	25	[0.469 – 1.232]	<.0001
	Manure	1.246 ^b	0.304	4	[0.650 – 1.842]	<.0001
	Rec. water	0.862 ^a	0.209	22	[0.452– 1.271]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.376	0.144		[-0.659 – -0.093]	0.010
	Before 2000					0.328
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1717	QE(df=113)		QM(df=5)	
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0550	p<.001		p<.001	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0075				
	s^2 (residual)	0.4447				
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.153
	Points removed	1				
	Children	Fixed effects				
MultiOR						
Drink water		1.596 ^c	0.284	9	[1.038 – 2.153]	<.0001
Farm		1.488 ^b	0.278	7	[0.944 – 2.032]	<.0001
Playground		0.788 ^a	0.252	8	[0.293 – 1.282]	<.0001
Rec water		1.543 ^{bc}	0.294	6	[0.967 – 2.120]	<.0001
UniOR		-0.438	0.264		[-0.956 – 0.080]	0.097
Before 2000		-0.638	0.217		[-1.064 – 0.213]	0.003
Random effects						
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)		0.0615	QE(df=23)		QM(df=4)	
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)		0.0079	p=0.715		p<0.001	
s^2 (residual)		0.2600				
Publication bias		-0.0003	0.0002			0.052
Points removed		1				

In both the mixed and children population, the environmental pathways under study were significantly associated with disease ($p < .0001$ in Table 4B). On meta-analysis, adults who handled garden soil and manure presented odds of infection 3.476 times higher (95% CI: 1.915 – 6.309) than those who did not. At a lower level of risk laid the other environmental pathways which the mixed population was exposed to – attendance to day care (overall OR=2.387; 95% CI: 1.448 – 3.935), contaminated drink water (overall OR=2.264; 95% CI: 1.567 – 3.267), farm environment (overall OR=2.340; 95% CI: 1.598 – 3.428) and recreational water (overall OR=2.368; 95% CI: 1.571 – 3.564), and they were not significantly different among themselves. As a whole, through the same environmental exposures, children presented higher odds of becoming infected than the mixed population; with pooled OR 4.933 (95% CI: 2.823 – 8.611) from contaminated drink water, OR 4.428 (95% CI: 2.570 – 7.629) from farm environment, and OR 4.679 (95% CI: 2.630 – 8.331) from recreational water. The playground subcategory, which included diverse exposures such as playing with soil, playing in parks, being in shopping cart next to raw meat, playing in area with bird droppings, playing in sandbox, and snow/sand in mouth, bore a significantly lower risk of transmission of campylobacteriosis (overall OR=2.199; 95% CI: 1.340 – 3.604; Table 4B). After Cook's distance assessment, one potentially-biased and influential OR measure was removed from each of the meta-analyses (Table 4B). In addition, the OR measures appeared to be reasonably distributed with the funnel plots from both, the mixed and children population meta-analyses (Figure 6). However, in the latter meta-analysis, publication bias was likely since the case-control study size affected the measures of OR ($p=0.053$; Table 4B).

Figure 6. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis on person-to-person transmission of campylobacteriosis by geographical region was only performed on 17 OR measures, with very few data points for Asia (2), North America (1), Northern Europe (2) and Oceania (3), reason as to why the overall ORs from those regions were considered to be not representative enough to make any meaningful comparisons (Table 5A). A higher number of OR measures could be extracted from Western European case-control studies (9), which, on meta-analysis, corroborated that person-to-person contagion was a significant source of campylobacteriosis (pooled OR=1.662; $p < .0001$

in Table 5A). However, taking all geographical regions together, and grouping instead by type of population produced marked differences: contact with an ill person rendered the children population (overall OR=4.216; 95% CI: 2.208 – 8.052) significantly more likely to become infected than the mixed population (overall OR=1.721; 95% CI: 1.075 – 2.757; Table 5B). In this meta-analysis, the sole variable “type of population” accounted for most of the variability in ORs between case-control studies ($p=0.109$ in the QE statistic). While there was no influential point removed in this meta-analysis, no file-drawer problem was evident either in the formal study size effect test ($p=0.093$ in Table 5A) or in the funnel plot (Figure 7).

Table 5A. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of *Campylobacter* by region for the combined mixed (n=9) and children (n=8) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
Asia	1.091	0.415	2	[0.276 – 1.906]	0.009
North America	0.955	0.417	1	[0.138 – 1.773]	0.022
North Europe	-0.312	0.377	2	[-1.050 – 0.427]	0.408
Oceania	1.185	0.272	3	[0.652 – 1.718]	<.0001
West Europe	0.508	0.113	9	[0.287 – 0.729]	<.0001

Table 5B. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of *Campylobacter* for the combined mixed (n=9) and children (n=8) population – no geographical region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
MultiOR					
Children	1.439 ^b	0.330	8	[0.792 – 2.086]	<.0001
Mixed	0.543 ^a	0.240	9	[0.073– 1.014]	0.024
UniOR	-0.448	0.554		[-1.533 – 0.636]	0.418
Before 2000	0.559	0.222		[0.125 – 0.993]	0.012
Random effects					
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.1593	QE(df=13)		QM(df=2)	
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.3438	$p=0.109$		$p<.001$	
s^2 (residual)	0.2823				
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.093
Points removed	0				

Figure 7. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of *Campylobacter* in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Most of the routes of transmission of campylobacteriosis recovered in the systematic review were related to consumption of food, for which a total of 714 OR measures were extracted and categorised. In the mixed population, the ingestion of contaminated foods was associated with acquiring campylobacteriosis in the different geographical regions to the same degree: North America (overall OR=1.660), Northern Europe (overall OR=1.473), Oceania (overall OR=1.608) and Western Europe (overall OR=1.514; Table 6A). In the children population, as occurred in other exposure categories, the global association measures were slightly higher (ORs between 1.374 – 1.940) than those of the mixed population, except for the Asian region, where a non-significant overall OR (1.103; $p=0.808$) was found. Thus, the Asian case-control studies were removed from the children data set for the next meta-analysis on food pathways by subcategory.

The meta-analysis on food consumption pathways demonstrated that food from all categories could act as potential determinants of campylobacteriosis (see all $p<.0001$ in Table 6B). At this level of grouping (i.e., broader data partition), meta-analysis made it possible to establish which food categories were more or less associated with disease. In the mixed population, produce – including fruits, vegetables, spices and roots – was the food pathway least associated with campylobacteriosis at an overall OR 1.477 (95% CI: 1.221 – 1.788; Table 6B). At a higher association level laid both the seafood pathways (overall OR=1.800; 95% CI: 1.474 – 2.201) – mainly comprised of fish, oysters, shellfish and raw seafood – and composite foods (overall OR=1.800; 95% CI: 1.493 – 2.168). The category of beverages, represented by bottled water purchased in Ireland, UK, Norway, Finland, USA, Canada and Australia, presented as high a level of association with campylobacteriosis (overall OR=1.868; 95% CI: 1.533 – 2.277) as the broad category of meats and meat products (overall OR=1.933; 95% CI: 1.611 – 2.319). Dairy products, which were made up basically of raw milk, unpasteurised milk cheese and soft cheese (overall OR=2.063; 95% CI: 1.683 – 2.524), and eggs, comprising mostly raw eggs and mayonnaise (overall OR=2.056; 95% CI: 1.683 – 2.524), had both a slightly higher association with campylobacteriosis than meat. The grains category was not ranked among the others, since data points available were so few that an unreliable (uncertain) pooled estimate was produced (overall OR=1.954; 95% CI: 1.331 – 2.869; Table 6B).

Table 6A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission by region for mixed (n=623) and children/susceptible (n=91) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.507	0.134	186	[0.245 – 0.770]	<.0001
North Europe	0.387	0.089	249	[0.213 – 0.561]	<.0001
Oceania	0.475	0.158	84	[0.165 – 0.784]	0.003
West Europe	0.415	0.146	104	[0.129 – 0.701]	0.005
Children					
Asia	0.098	0.404	9	[-0.694 – 0.891]	0.808
East Europe	0.648	0.322	8	[0.016 – 1.280]	0.044
North America	0.663	0.295	15	[0.085 – 1.241]	0.025
North Europe	0.493	0.265	7	[-0.026 – 1.012]	0.063
Oceania	0.318	0.242	30	[-0.156 – 0.792]	0.189
West Europe	0.762	0.286	22	[0.201 – 1.323]	0.008

Table 6B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission for mixed (n=623) and children/susceptible (n=80) population – Asian countries removed from the children population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed						
	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Beverages	0.625 ^c	0.101	19	[0.427 – 0.823]	<.0001
	Composite	0.588 ^b	0.095	54	[0.401 – 0.774]	<.0001
	Dairy (raw)	0.724 ^d	0.103	47	[0.521 – 0.926]	<.0001
	Eggs (raw)	0.721 ^{cd}	0.163	5	[0.402 – 1.040]	<.0001
	Grains	0.670 ^{abcd}	0.196	4	[0.286 – 1.054]	<.0001
	Meat	0.659 ^c	0.093	427	[0.477 – 0.841]	<.0001
	Produce	0.390 ^a	0.098	49	[0.200 – 0.581]	<.0001
	Seafood	0.588 ^b	0.104	18	[0.388 – 0.789]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.290	0.028		[-0.344 – -0.235]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.275
	Random effects					

s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1364	QE(df=612)		QM(df=8)	
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0189	p<.0001		p<.0001	
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0225				
s^2 (residual)	0.5661				
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.016
Points removed	2				
Children/ Infants	Fixed effects				
	MultiOR				
	Composite	0.836 ^a	0.184	11	[0.476 – 1.197] <.0001
	Dairy	1.168 ^c	0.210	15	[0.757 – 1.757] <.0001
	Eggs (raw)	1.018 ^b	0.216	9	[0.593 – 1.442] <.0001
	Meat	0.897 ^a	0.164	36	[0.576 – 1.218] <.0001
	Produce	0.985 ^{ab}	0.207	7	[0.579 – 1.390] <.0001
	Seafood	0.874 ^a	0.466	2	[-0.39 – 1.787] 0.061
	UniOR	-0.365	0.137		[-0.634 – -0.096] 0.008
	Before 2000	-0.392	0.237		[-0.857 – 0.072] 0.098
	Random effects				
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0718	QE(df=72)		QM(df=6)	
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0041	p=0.001		p<.0001	
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0047				
s^2 (residual)	0.3082				
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0002			0.115
Points removed	0				

In the children population, for each the food categories where data were available, composite, dairy, eggs, meat, produce and seafood, the meta-analysed ORs were higher (2.307 – 3.215) than those of the mixed population. Children who consumed contaminated composite food (overall OR=2.307; 95% CI: 1.609 – 3.310), contaminated meat (overall OR=2.452; 95% CI: 1.778 – 3.380), and contaminated produce (overall OR=2.678; 95% CI: 1.784 – 4.015) were at about equal (-ly high) odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis than those who did not. Children having any kind of raw-egg based preparation (overall OR=2.768; 95% CI: 1.809 – 4.229) as well as children aged 0-2 years having powder infant and children younger than 6 years old having any unpasteurised dairy product (overall OR=3.216; 95% CI: 2.131 – 5.795) were slightly more exposed to campylobacteriosis. As data on seafood consumed by children consisted only of two ORs, no meaningful conclusion with regards to this food pathway could be gained (Table 6B). While two data points were removed from the mixed population meta-analysis for being potentially biased and influential, all data points were kept for the children meta-analysis. In the mixed population, there was evidence that the smaller the case-control study size, the higher the OR measures (p=0.016 in Table 6B), thus suggesting the possibility of some file-drawer problems for small studies associated to non-significant results (i.e., ORs

not showing association between food consumption and disease). This can also be deduced from the funnel plot shown in Figure 8 (left). In the case of the children-population meta-analysis, the dispersion of OR observations within the funnel appeared better behaved (Figure 8, right).

Figure 8. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Amongst all the food subcategories, meat was the one whose multiple exposures were the most investigated in case-control studies (producing 471 ORs). In all of the geographical areas, meat was an important vehicle for acquiring campylobacteriosis ($p < .0001$) by the mixed population, with overall OR values ranging from 1.496 to 1.775 (Table 7A). In children, the mean associations were slightly higher, between 1.222 and 2.168, for the same geographical regions. In the case-control studies conducted in Asian countries, the pooled OR (1.131; $p = 0.718$; Table 7A) was the lowest among all regions. So, these data were not considered in the following general meta-analysis by meat class.

Within meats, pork consumption bore the lowest risk of campylobacteriosis: On meta-analysis, those who ate pork meat had 1.204 (95% CI: 1.016 – 1.423; Table 7B) greater probability of acquiring the disease than those who were not exposed. A slightly higher association was found for the meat categories of beef (overall OR=1.429; 95% CI: 1.216 – 1.679); other red meats, encompassing horse, lamb, mutton, game, and unspecified halaal meat (overall OR=1.339; 95% CI: 1.117 – 1.602); and processed meat, made up of sausages, pate, ham, bacon, salami, jerky and meat pies (overall OR=1.350; 95% CI: 1.157 – 1.575). In the mixed population, campylobacteriosis was more strongly associated with the consumption of poultry. The meta-analysis of 244 OR measures extracted from the literature, which consisted of different kinds of chicken preparations such as BBQ chicken, chicken fondue, chicken pieces, chicken giblets, grilled, fried and roasted chicken, produced a high pooled OR (1.779; 95% CI: 1.540 – 2.052; Table 7B). Interestingly, the “Other Meats” category, which was created to accommodate meat of non-specified origin, presented the highest association with campylobacteriosis at a pooled OR of 2.210 (95% CI: 1.900 – 2.570). This category encompassed meat fondue, BBQ meat, grilled meat, minced meat, offal and tripe.

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter*-transmission by region for mixed (n=427) and children (n=44) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.574	0.148	121	[0.279 – 0.861]	<.0001
North Europe	0.403	0.089	164	[0.229 – 0.577]	<.0001
Oceania	0.522	0.165	63	[0.198 – 0.846]	0.001
West Europe	0.442	0.142	79	[0.165 – 0.720]	0.002
Children					
Asia	0.123	0.342	8	[-0.547 – 0.794]	0.718
East Europe	0.702	0.289	4	[0.136 – 1.268]	0.015
North America	0.504	0.274	5	[-0.034 – 1.042]	0.066
North Europe	0.774	0.317	4	[0.152 – 1.396]	0.015
Oceania	0.201	0.263	13	[-0.314 – 0.717]	0.444
West Europe	1.001	0.313	10	[0.387 – 1.614]	0.001

For the children population, as few data points were available in the beef (3 ORs), pork and other red meats (4 ORs) and processed meats (5 ORs) classes, there was high uncertainty about their pooled ORs (95% CI: 1.219 – 4.237; 1.363 – 4.027; 1.253 – 3.792, respectively). This prevented to make any conclusive comparisons among them. When considering the meat classes for which more extracted ORs were available – poultry and other meats – the same trend, observed in the mixed population, was displayed in the children population. This is, the children affected by campylobacteriosis were slightly more likely to have consumed BBQ/grill meats (overall OR=2.291; 95% CI: 1.579 – 3.320) than chicken (overall OR=2.077; 95% CI: 1.378 – 3.127; Table 7B), in comparison to non-affected children. The statistical test for publication bias failed to detect any significant effect of case-control study size on the OR values they measured, either in the mixed (p=0.129) or in the children population (p=0.823; Table 7B).

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter*-transmission for mixed (n=427) and children (n=31) population – Asia removed from the children population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
	Beef	0.357 ^b	0.082	44	[0.196 – 0.518]	<.0001	
	Other red meat	0.292 ^b	0.091	14	[0.111 – 0.471]	<.0001	
	Others	0.793 ^d	0.077	62	[0.642 – 0.944]	<.0001	
	Pork	0.186 ^a	0.086	22	[0.016 – 0.355]	0.032	
	Poultry	0.576 ^c	0.073	227	[0.432 – 0.719]	<.0001	
	Proc meat	0.300 ^b	0.078	58	[0.146 – 0.454]	<.0001	
	UniOR	-0.196	0.031		[-0.256 – -0.135]	<.0001	
	Before 2000	0.156	0.103		[-0.046 – 0.358]	0.130	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0908	QE(df=417)		QM(df=6)		
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0001	p<.0001		p<.0001		
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0001					
	s^2 (residual)	0.6398					
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000				0.129
	Points removed	2					
Children/ Infants	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
	Beef	0.821 ^b	0.318	3	[0.198 – 1.444]	0.009	
	Pork&red meats	0.852 ^b	0.276	4	[0.310 – 1.393]	0.002	
	Others	0.829 ^b	0.189	8	[0.457 – 1.200]	<.0001	
	Poultry	0.731 ^a	0.209	11	[0.321 – 1.140]	0.001	
	Proc meat	0.780 ^a	0.282	5	[0.226 – 1.333]	0.006	
	UniOR	-0.086	0.221		[-0.519 – 0.348]	0.698	
	Before 2000	-0.478	0.171		[-0.813 - -0.144]	0.005	
	Random effects						
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0026	QE(df=23)		QM(df=5)		
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0057	p=0.688		p<0.001		
	s^2 (residual)	0.2085					
	Publication bias	0.0001	0.0004				0.823
	Points removed	1					

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In the questionnaires presented to cases and controls, previous consumption of eggs was seldom enquired. For the very few ORs (14), the responses given in North America (overall OR=1.506), Europe (overall OR=1.562) and Oceania (overall OR=1.400) were within the same range (Table 8A). In the meta-analysis by subcategory, the two egg classes – defined as eggs in the mixed population and raw-egg containing products in the children category – explained the between-study variability; therefore, the residual variability was non-significant ($p=0.715$; Table 8A). The consumption of mayonnaise or other products containing raw eggs posed a higher risk of disease (overall OR=4.845; 95% CI: 2.989 – 7.870) in children than the consumption of any eggs (overall OR=1.453; 95% CI: 1.085 – 1.944) in the mixed population (Table 8B). The funnel plot of this meta-analysis did not hint any evidence of publication bias (Figure 10), which was also supported by the non-significant effect of study size in the regression ($p=0.264$; Table 8B).

Table 8A. Meta-analyses of eggs consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter*-transmission by region for the combined mixed (n=5) and children (n=9) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.410	0.536	4	[-0.64 – 1.460]	0.444
West&North Europe	0.446	0.390	5	[-0.318 – 1.211]	0.253
Oceania	0.336	0.573	5	[-0.788 – 1.459]	0.558

Table 8B. Meta-analysis of eggs consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter*-transmission for combined mixed (n=5) and children (n=9) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed & Children	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Eggs	0.374 ^a	0.149	10	[0.082 – 0.665]	0.012
	Raw egg prods	1.578 ^b	0.246	4	[1.095 – 2.063]	<.0001
	Before 2000	-0.384	0.141		[-0.660 – -0.107]	0.006
	Random effects					
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0050	QE(df=10)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0235	p=0.715		p<0.001	
	s^2 (residual)	0.1279				
	Publication bias	0.0002	0.0002			0.264
	Points removed	1				

Figure 10. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of eggs consumption pathways for *Campylobacter* infection in the combined mixed and children population

Data on exposures related to consumption of milk and dairy products were available from case-control studies conducted in North America, North Europe, Oceania and Western Europe for both the mixed and the children population. In the mixed population, North American cases presented an overall association between dairy foods and campylobacteriosis of OR=2.134, which was higher than those of Northern Europe (overall OR=1.499) and Western Europe (overall OR=1.005; Table 9A). In Northern Europe (overall OR=4.554) and Western Europe (overall OR=2.866), children were more susceptible of acquiring campylobacteriosis

through the dairy consumption route than the mixed population. No geographical region was removed for the general meta-analysis by dairy class.

Table 9A. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission by region for mixed (n=47) and children (n=15) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.758	0.210	19	[0.346 – 1.170]	<.0001
North Europe	0.405	0.157	18	[0.098 – 0.712]	0.001
Oceania	1.312	0.505	3	[0.323 – 2.301]	0.001
West Europe	0.005	0.298	7	[-0.580 – 0.589]	0.987
Children					
North America	0.714	0.312	3	[0.102 – 1.325]	0.022
North Europe	1.516	0.442	2	[0.651 – 2.382]	0.001
Oceania	0.460	0.198	5	[0.073 – 0.847]	0.020
West Europe	1.053	0.290	5	[0.484 – 1.623]	<.0001

Figure 11. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In the mixed population, the weakest association with campylobacteriosis was posed by the dairy fats class (represented by butter, unpasteurised cream and ice-cream) with an overall OR of 1.448 (95% CI: 0.647 – 3.238; Table 9B). The cheese class – composed of any cheese, fresh and soft cheese (overall OR=1.724; 95% CI: 0.973 – 3.056) – presented the same level of risk of campylobacteriosis as the undefined class, comprising the exposures “any raw dairy product” and “any dairy product” (overall OR=1.861; 95% 1.034 – 3.343). At a higher risk of

campylobacteriosis laid the consumption of non-pasteurised milk by the mixed population (overall OR=2.640; 95% CI: 1.738 – 4.007). The same trend was observed in the children population: this is, children who consumed raw milk (overall OR=3.053; 95% CI: 1.925 – 4.831) were more likely to acquire campylobacteriosis than those who consumed raw milk's cheese and dairy fats (overall OR=1.986; 95% CI: 1.186 – 3.327). Infants younger than 2 years on powdered formula diet were seemingly at higher risk of campylobacteriosis (overall OR=5.012; 95% CI: 1.307 – 19.20), although as it was meta-analysed from only 3 OR measures, it should be interpreted with caution. In both meta-analyses, there were no potentially-biased OR estimates spotted by the Cook's distance assessment.

Table 9B. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission for mixed (n=46) and children (n=15) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Cheese	0.545 ^b	0.292	5	[-0.027 – 1.117]	0.062
	Fats	0.370 ^a	0.411	3	[-0.436 – 1.175]	0.368
	Milk	0.971 ^c	0.213	32	[0.553 – 1.388]	<.0001
	Undefined	0.621 ^b	0.300	6	[0.034 – 1.207]	0.038
	UniOR	-0.365	0.194		[-0.745– 0.016]	0.060
	Before 2000					0.478
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2415	QE(df=40)		QM(df=4)	
	s ² (residual)	0.6358	p<.001		p<.001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.402
	Points removed	0				
Children	Fixed effects					
	Milk	1.116 ^b	0.235	8	[0.655 – 1.575]	<.0001
	Powder	1.612 ^b	0.685	3	[0.268 – 2.955]	0.019
	Cheese&Fats	0.686 ^a	0.263	4	[0.171 – 1.202]	0.009
	Before 2000	-0.517	0.311		[-1.127 – 0.094]	0.097
	Random effects		QE(df=11)		QE(df=3)	
	s ² (residual)	0.2947	p=0.547		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0018	0.0008			0.022
	Points removed	0				

The meta-analysis on seafood pathways of transmission by geographical region showed that in Northern and Western Europe, there may be only a very weak association, if any, between seafood and campylobacteriosis (overall OR=1.027; p=0.849) whereas in North America consumption of seafood can be considered as a potential determinant of campylobacteriosis (overall OR=1.432; p=0.086; Table 10A). Because of the limited number of OR measures available within this route of exposure, no geographical region was removed for the subsequent meta-analysis by seafood class. Data from the mixed and children population were meta-analysed together. The most innocuous kind of seafood, in terms of human infection with campylobacteriosis, corresponded to the processed fish/shellfish with an overall OR of 0.753 (95% CI: 0.531 – 1.067) and fish with a pooled OR of 0.962 (95% CI: 0.705 – 1.313; Table 10B). On average, people who ate molluscs had 1.200 times (95% CI: 0.897 – 1.605) higher probability of acquiring campylobacteriosis than those who did not. Eating raw seafood bore the highest risk of becoming infected (overall OR=1.502; 95% CI: 1.052 – 2.145; Table 10B). In this meta-analysis, no potentially-biased OR was influential, and publication bias could not be proved (Figure 12; Table 10B)

Table 10A. Meta-analysis of seafood-related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission by region for the combined mixed (n=17) and children (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed & Children					
North America	0.359	0.209	11	[-0.051 – 0.771]	0.086
North&West Europe	0.027	0.144	8	[-0.255 – 0.309]	0.849

Table 10B. Meta-analysis of seafood-related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission for the combined mixed (n=17) and children (n=2) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	Fish	-0.039 ^b	0.159	5	[-0.349 – 0.272]	0.807
	Molluscs	0.182 ^c	0.149	6	[-0.109 – 0.473]	0.222
	Processed	-0.284 ^a	0.178	4	[-0.633 – 0.065]	0.110
	Raw seafood	0.407 ^d	0.182	4	[0.051 – 0.763]	0.025
	Before 2000					0.196
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0496	QE(df=15)		QM(df=4)	
	s ² (residual)	0.1685	p=0.065		p=0.021	
	Publication bias	0.0003	0.0002			0.109
	Points removed	0				

Figure 12. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In the mixed population, the meta-analysis model on produce by geographical region did not encounter any association between consumption of produce and campylobacteriosis in the case-control studies from North America (OR=0.967; p=0.938), Oceania (OR=0.633; p=0.262) and Western Europe (OR=1.017; p=0.946 in Table 11A). When combining the case-control studies only from Northern Europe, the conclusion was opposite: the consumption of produce by the mixed population could bring about infection with *Campylobacter* spp. (OR=1.534; p=0.010). In the children population, the pooled ORs available only for North America (OR=3.367) and Oceania (OR=1.394) were higher, although very uncertain due to the few data points available (Table 11A). All geographical regions were kept for the meta-analysis by produce class.

Table 11A. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission by region for mixed (n=49) and children (n=6) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	-0.033	0.423	10	[-0.862 – 0.796]	0.938
North Europe	0.428	0.168	20	[0.099 – 0.757]	0.010
Oceania	-0.457	0.408	13	[-1.256 – 0.342]	0.262
West Europe	0.017	0.250	6	[-0.474 – 0.508]	0.946
Children					
North America	1.214	0.385	3	[0.458 – 1.969]	0.002
Oceania	0.332	0.364	3	[-0.380 – 1.044]	0.361

Table 11B. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission for mixed (n=49) and children (n=7) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Fruits	0.290 ^b	0.218	18	[-0.137 – 0.717]	0.183
	Fungi&Spices	0.041 ^a	0.229	4	[-0.407 – 0.489]	0.858
	Sprouts	0.125 ^a	0.269	3	[-0.402 – 0.652]	0.642
	Vegetables	0.317 ^b	0.216	24	[-0.107 – 0.740]	0.143
	UniOR	-0.153	0.259		[-0.660 – 0.354]	0.554
	Before 2000					0.629
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1958	QE(df=43)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0492	p<.001		p=0.013	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0309				
	s^2 (residual)	0.3000				
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0001			0.757
	Points removed	1				
Children	Fixed effects					
	Herbs	1.271 ^b	0.514	3	[0.263 – 2.279]	0.013
	Vegs&Fruits	0.432 ^a	0.258	4	[-0.074 – 0.939]	0.095
	Before 2000					0.624
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3327	QE(df=5)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3244	p=0.020		p=0.047	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0015			0.944
	Points removed	0				

In the mixed population, very weak – or no – association between campylobacter and consumption of produce was found for fungi and fresh herbs (overall OR=1.042; 95% CI: 0.665 – 1.631) and sprouts (overall OR=1.133; 95% CI: 0.669 – 1.919 in Table 11B). The consumption of fruits (p=0.183) and vegetables (p=0.143) presented a higher association with disease: people who consumed fruits presented overall 1.336 (95% CI: 0.872 – 2.048) times the odds of becoming ill than those who did not, which was not significantly different than those who consumed vegetables (overall OR=1.373; 95% CI: 0.898 – 2.096; Table 11B). On the other hand, children were more susceptible of becoming infected with *Campylobacter* through the consumption of contaminated produce. However, contrarily to what was observed

in the mixed population, children who consumed raw cilantro and basil (i.e, herbs – overall OR=3.564; 95% CI: 1.301 – 9.767) were at higher odds of becoming infected than those who consumed vegetables and fruits (overall OR=1.540; 95% CI: 0.929 – 2.557 in Table 11B). In none of these meta-analyses, there was evidence of publication bias (Table 11B; Figure 13).

Figure 13. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of produce consumption pathways for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Most of the data on consumption of beverages as potential determinant of campylobacteriosis was produced in Northern European case-control studies (15 ORs), whose meta-analysis evidenced some association between pathway and disease (OR=1.262; p=0.024 in Table 12A) in such a region. When conducting the meta-analysis by beverage class, which integrated data from all geographical regions, no significant risk of disease from the consumption of alcoholic beverages was found (overall OR=0.958; 95% CI: 0.733 – 1.252 in Table 12B). However, bottled water was proven to be a source of campylobacteriosis: on meta-analysis, nationals from USA, UK, Norway, Greece, Canada, Finland and Australia who drank bottled water had 1.392 (95% CI: 1.225 – 1.581) times the odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis that those who did not. Whereas no potentially-biased OR was found to be influential, the existence of publication bias was not evident (Table 12B, Figure 14)

Table 12A. Meta-analysis of beverage consumption as risk factor for *Campylobacter*-transmission by region for the combined mixed (n=19) and children (n=1) population – no region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
North America	0.023	0.254	2	[-0.474 – 0.521]	0.927
North Europe	0.233	0.103	15	[0.031 – 0.435]	0.024
Oceania	0.628	0.233	3	[0.171 – 1.085]	0.007

Table 12B. Meta-analysis of beverage consumption as risk factor for *Campylobacter*-transmission for the combined mixed (n=19) and children (n=1) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Alcoholic	-0.043 ^a	0.136	3	[-0.310 – 0.225]	0.755
Bottled water	0.331 ^b	0.065	17	[0.203 – 0.458]	<.0001
Before 2000					0.531
Random effects					
s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0247	QE(df=18)		QM(df=2)	
s ² (residual)	0.1300	p<.0001		p<.0001	
Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.894
Points removed	0				

Figure 14. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of beverage consumption for *Campylobacter* infection in the combined mixed and children population

Composite foods constituted an important source of campylobacteriosis in the mixed population, particularly in Northern Europe (overall OR=1.354; p<.0001) and Western Europe (overall OR=1.426; p=0.001). In European children, the extent of association between composite foods and campylobacteriosis (overall OR=1.408; p=0.180) was comparable to that of the mixed population (Table 13A). The general meta-analysis by composite food class pointed that composite fast-food (overall OR=1.586; 95% CI: 1.347 – 1.866) and composite dishes (overall OR=1.369; 95% CI: 1.241 – 1.507) presented the highest association with campylobacteriosis in the mixed population (Table 13B). While fast-food included composite food from chicken outlets, kebab house, Indian take-away and fast-food from street vendors, the dishes class was made up of dishes mostly prepared outside home (63%). RTE composite

foods bore the lowest pooled OR (1.227; 95% CI: 1.092 – 1.380), although still significant. On meta-analysis, children with campylobacteriosis were on average 2.161 (95% CI: 1.076 – 4.340) times more likely to have consumed any multi-ingredient food than well children. In the mixed population’s meta-analysis, the observations were well dispersed within the funnel plot, therefore giving no clue for the presence of publication bias (Figure 15, left). In the children population’s meta-analysis, despite the few OR measures available, the funnel plot was still well behaved (Figure 15, right). Only one potentially-biased OR turned out to be an influential data point in the regression, and was therefore removed from the mixed population’s analysis (Table 13B).

Table 13A. Meta-analyses of composite-food related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission by region for the mixed (n=54) and children (n=11) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.117	0.107	20	[-0.093– 0.327]	0.274
North Europe	0.303	0.072	25	[0.163 – 0.443]	<.0001
Oceania	0.895	0.201	2	[0.502 – 1.289]	<.0001
West Europe	0.355	0.110	7	[0.139 – 0.571]	0.001
Children					
North America	0.884	0.463	3	[-0.023 – 1.790]	0.056
Oceania	0.009	0.404	2	[-0.784 – 0.801]	0.983
Europe	0.342	0.255	6	[-0.158 – 0.843]	0.180

Figure 15. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for *Campylobacter* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 13B. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for *Campylobacter* transmission for the mixed (n=52) and children (n=9) population – Oceania was removed from the mixed and children population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Dishes	0.314 ^b	0.050	35	[0.216 – 0.410]	<.0001
	Fast-food	0.461 ^c	0.083	12	[0.298 – 0.624]	<.0001
	RTE	0.205 ^a	0.060	5	[0.088 – 0.322]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.105	0.058		[-0.219 – 0.009]	0.071
	Before 2000					0.575
	Random effects					
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0004	QE(df=47)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0009	p=0.005		p<.0001	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3160				
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.522
	Points removed	1				
	Children	Fixed effects				
MultiOR						
All composite		0.771	0.355	9	[0.074 – 1.468]	0.030
UniOR		-0.338	0.308		[-0.941 – 0.265]	0.272
Random effects						
s^2_u (Intercept)		0.1731	QE(df=7)			
s^2 (residual)		0.2451	p<.0001			
Publication bias		-0.0004	0.0002			0.039
Points removed	0					

3.2.3 Meta-analysis on the risk of *Campylobacter* transmission by ready-to-eat foods and barbecued foods

Integrating the outcomes from the case-control studies undertaken in Northern Europe (overall OR=1.188; p=0.121), Western Europe (overall OR=1.343; p=0.244) and Oceania (overall OR=1.416; p=0.054), RTE foods could be regarded as a potential vehicle for transmission of *Campylobacter*. By contrary, there was no evidence for RTE foods from North America to be a source of transmission of campylobacteriosis (overall OR=1.026; p=0.905 in Table 14A).

The meta-analysis estimated that people who consumed RTE foods had 1.196 (95% CI: 1.011 – 1.416) times higher probability of acquiring campylobacteriosis than those who were not exposed by consumption (Table 14B). Meta-analysing by RTE class, it was found that the meat-based RTE foods (including RTE beef, RTE chicken and RTE processed meats) bore higher risk of infection (overall OR=1.210; 95% CI: 1.019 – 1.436) than the dairy based RTE foods (overall OR=1.111; 95% CI: 0.857 – 1.437). The test for publication bias implied that the larger the case-control study size, the smaller the OR that was measured ($p=0.012$; Table 14B). Hence, it is possible that low-powered studies failing to find a significant OR remained unpublished. However, the even spread of data points within the funnel plot (Figure 16, left) does not hint any strong file-drawer problem.

Table 14A. Meta-analysis of the risk of *Campylobacter* transmission due to consumption of RTE foods by region in the combined mixed (n=53) and children (n=8) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
North America	0.026	0.220	24	[-0.405 – 0.457]	0.905
North Europe	0.172	0.111	22	[-0.045 – 0.389]	0.121
Oceania	0.348	0.181	11	[-0.006 – 0.703]	0.054
West Europe	0.295	0.254	4	[-0.202 – 0.793]	0.244

Table 14B. Meta-analysis of the risk of *Campylobacter* transmission due to consumption of RTE foods overall and by food category in the combined mixed (n=40) and children (n=5) population. No region was removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All RTE foods	0.179	0.086	45	[0.011 – 0.348]	0.037
Fixed effects					
Dairy-based	0.105 ^a	0.132	9	[-0.154 – 0.363]	0.428
Meat-based	0.191 ^a	0.087	36	[0.019 – 0.362]	0.029
Before 2000					0.564
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0835	QE(df=43)		QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)	0.2712	$p<.0001$		$p=0.086$	
Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.012
Points removed	0				

Figure 16. Funnel plots of the meta-analysis of RTE foods (left) and BBQ meats (right) as risk factors for *Campylobacter* infection. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

With regards to BBQ meats, in the three regions for which data were available, Northern Europe (overall OR=1.738), Western Europe (overall OR=1.828), and Oceania (overall OR=2.140), the consumption of BBQ meats was demonstrated to be an important vehicle of transmission of campylobacteriosis ($p < .0001$; Table 15A). On meta-analysis, consuming BBQ meats increased the risk of acquiring campylobacteriosis by 1.668 (95% CI: 1.259 – 2.208; Table 15B). The assessment of influential data points by Cook’s distance did not lead to the removal of any potentially-biased OR. The significant inverse effect of study size on the OR measure ($p = 0.057$; Table 15B) suggested the likely existence of publication bias, which was modestly implied by the funnel plot (Figure 16, right).

Table 15A. Meta-analysis of the risk of *Campylobacter* transmission due to consumption of BBQ meats by region in the combined mixed ($n = 45$) and children ($n = 4$) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
North Europe	0.553	0.115	31	[0.329 – 0.778]	<.0001
Oceania	0.761	0.236	5	[0.298 – 1.222]	0.001
West Europe	0.603	0.178	13	[0.254 – 0.951]	0.001

Table 15B. Meta-analysis of the risk of *Campylobacter* transmission due to consumption of BBQ meats by the combined mixed (n=45) and children population (n=4)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
MultiOR					
BBQ meats	0.512	0.143	49	[0.231 – 0.792]	<.0001
UniOR	-0.111	0.100		[-0.306 – 0.083]	0.262
Before 2000	0.273	0.186		[-0.092 – 0.638]	0.143
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0746	QE(df=46)			
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0057	p<.0001			
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0304				
s^2 (residual)	2.0107				
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.057
Points removed	0				

All the risk factors and pathways of exposure meta-analysed were brought together by means of forest plots. To visualise the most important routes of transmission of campylobacteriosis, their ORs were ranked in decreasing order (Figures 17 and 18). It was noticed that some pathways of exposure which had high pooled OR estimates had also high uncertainty: namely, milk powder in infants, farm animals in children, pets in children, spices in children, cheese and fats in children, cheese in the mixed population, travel inside and dairy fats in the mixed population. This arose from the limited data available in those categories. Disregarding these risk factors, the most important determinants of campylobacteriosis in children are: contaminated drinking water (overall OR=4.93; 95% CI: 2.82 – 8.62), consumption of raw-egg containing products (overall OR=4.85; 95% CI: 2.99 – 7.85), exposure to recreational water (overall OR=4.68; 95% CI: 2.63 – 8.32), exposure to farm/rural environment (overall OR=4.43; 95% CI: 2.57 – 7.63), person-to-person contagion (overall OR=4.22; 95% CI: 2.21 – 8.05), consumption of raw milk (overall OR=3.05; 95% CI: 1.93 – 4.84), pork (overall OR=2.34; 95% CI: 1.36 – 4.03), other meats (overall OR=2.29; 95% CI: 1.58 – 3.32), minced beef (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.22 – 4.24), exposure through playground (overall OR=2.20; 95% CI: 1.34 – 3.61), processed meats (overall OR=2.18; 95% CI: 1.25 – 3.80), any composite food (overall OR=2.16; 95% CI: 1.08 – 4.34) and poultry (overall OR=2.08; 95% CI: 1.38 – 3.13).

While the mixed population presented lower pooled ORs than the children, the most important determinants of campylobacteriosis in the mixed population were those related to travel, animal- and environmental sources of transmission and host-specific factors. Except for the consumption of raw milk (OR=2.64), the highest pooled ORs between 2.06 and 3.48 corresponded to the travel, animal/environmental routes of transmission and host-specific factors; namely: handling of manure (overall OR=3.48; 95% CI: 1.92 – 6.31), international travel (overall OR=3.05; 95% CI: 2.09 – 4.45), occupational exposure to

animals/carcasses/meat (overall OR=2.96; 95% CI: 2.30 – 3.80), recent use of anti-acids (overall OR=2.91; 95% CI: 2.10 – 4.05), contact with farm animals (overall OR=2.44; 95% CI: 2.01 – 2.97), attendance to day care (overall OR=2.39; 95% CI: 1.45 – 3.94), exposure to recreational water (overall OR=2.37; 95% CI: 1.57 – 3.57), exposure to farm/rural environment (overall OR=2.34; 95% CI: 1.60 – 3.42), exposure to wild animals (overall OR=2.33; 95% CI: 1.56 – 3.45), contaminated drinking water (overall OR=2.26; 95% CI: 1.57 – 3.27), suffering from any chronic disease (overall OR=2.22; 95% CI: 1.54 – 3.21) and being under other medications or medical treatment (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 1.36 – 3.11).

Figure 17. Forest plot of the overall odds-ratios of acquiring campylobacteriosis for host-specific factors, travel, environmental, animal and food pathways by category and population type (mixed and children), ranked in decreasing order

Figure 18. Forest plot of the overall odds-ratios of acquiring campylobacteriosis for host-specific factors, environmental, animal and food pathways by category and population type (mixed and children), ranked in decreasing order (sequence of Figure 17)

In the mixed population, as a whole food consumption bear discernibly lower risk of transmission of campylobacteriosis (pooled ORs from 0.75 to 1.78) than the host-specific factors and environmental/animal routes (pooled ORs from 2.06 – 3.48), with only very few exceptions. Within the food vehicles of transmission, the highest associations between campylobacteriosis and food in the mixed population were observed for: raw milk (overall OR=2.64; 95% CI: 1.74 – 4.01), other (non-classifiable) meats (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.90 – 2.57), poultry (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 1.54 – 2.05), raw milk’s cheese (overall

OR=1.72; 95% CI: 0.97 – 3.06), BBQ meats (overall OR=1.67; 95% CI: 1.26 – 2.21), fast-food composite (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 1.35 – 1.87) and raw seafood (overall OR=1.50; 95% CI: 1.05 – 2.14). Foodstuffs that on meta-analysis had weak (pooled OR marginally higher than one) or non-significant association with campylobacteriosis in the mixed population were: vegetables, fruits, molluscs, sprouts, dairy-based RTE, fungi and spices, fish, alcoholic beverages and processed fish (Figure 18).

3.2.4 Meta-analysis on the effects of handling and setting on the risk of *Campylobacter* transmission by food consumption

For some food classes, for which relevant information on handling and setting was available, their effects were summarised. Full meta-analysis models adjusted on the food classes poultry, beef, processed meat, eggs, milk and cheese, seafood and composite dishes are shown in the supplementary Tables S1-S7. As realised with the sporadic salmonellosis meta-analysis, eating out can be regarded as an important risk of acquiring campylobacteriosis. People who ate poultry, beef, processed meats and composite dishes prepared outside home had their odds of infection significantly increased by 1.251 – 1.850 (Table 16).

Table 16. Meta-analysed effects of handling and setting on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Poultry	OR(Base)	1.660	1.469	1.877
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	2.236	1.887	2.648
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.384	1.243	1.541
	OR(Home)/OR(Base)	0.787	0.679	1.097
Beef	OR(Base)	1.381	1.001	1.906
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	1.881	1.328	2.664
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.667	1.145	2.427
Processed meat	OR(Base)	1.355	1.116	1.645
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.850	1.354	2.524
Eggs and egg products	OR(Base)	2.447	1.095	5.468
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.892	0.902	3.966
Milk and cheese	OR(Base)	0.980	0.683	1.403
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	2.420	1.624	3.607
Seafood	OR(Base)	0.984	0.856	1.131
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.624	1.269	2.079
Dishes	OR(Base)	1.082	0.789	1.486
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.251	0.900	1.745

Eating food prepared at home may instead have a protective effect, as it was the case of poultry, which, when prepared at home, reduced the odds of becoming infected by 1.27 (95% CI: 0.911 – 1.473; calculated from Table 16 as the reciprocal of the estimates presented). Eating undercooked meat was generally a risky practice, although eating rare chicken increased the odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis to a greater extent (overall OR=2.236; 95% CI: 1.887 – 2.648) than eating rare beef (overall OR=1.881; 95% CI: 1.328 – 2.664; Table 16) in comparison to the base scenario. On meta-analysis, people who consumed unpasteurised milk and raw milk's cheese had 2.420 (95% CI: 1.624 – 3.607) greater probability of getting campylobacteriosis than those who consumed *simply* dairy products (without having being specific as to whether they were raw). Although, to a lower extent than the dairy products, eating raw eggs and raw seafood also increased the odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis by 1.892 and 1.624 times, respectively (Table 16).

3.2.5 *Synthesis of the risks associated to ways of preparation and poor handling of foods*

Figures 19 and 20 graphically compiles all the exposures retrieved related to poor handling of foods and ways of preparation, with ranked measures of their capacity to trigger campylobacteriosis in the mixed and the children population. Some of the exposures listed in the poor handling forest plot (Figure 19) can explain the reasons why BBQ meats were associated with high risk of campylobacteriosis: namely, poor BBQ techniques (OR=4.40 – 4.60), use of same plate for raw and BBQ meat (OR=2.20 – 2.30), poor hygiene of utensils (OR=1.70 – 2.12) and flies on food (OR=1.46). Other poor practices in the kitchen were related to not washing knives after cutting raw meat (OR=1.50 – 1.70), and poor hygiene of hands (OR=1.60) and cutting boards (OR=1.30). The non-hygienic behaviour in the kitchen also affected the health of children, as keeping garbage uncovered (OR=2.47), use of same utensils for raw and cooked food without previous washing (OR=2.00) and keeping a dirty kitchen floor (OR=1.17) were found to increase the odds of children's becoming diseased (Figure 19).

Some food preparation practices that induce cross-contamination can also increase the odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis, such as: keeping raw poultry in the kitchen (OR=2.40 – 9.55) and inappropriate use of cutting board (OR=1.50 – 2.10). Tasting raw meat while cooking has been also proven to be a risky behaviour (OR=1.20 – 1.80). Proper washing of hands (OR=0.60), knives (OR=0.60) and counter top (OR=0.50) during food preparation are protective against campylobacteriosis (Figure 20). Children may be exposed to campylobacteriosis when raw chicken is kept in kitchen (OR=2.86 – 4.14), poultry is being thawed in kitchen (OR=3.10 – 4.00), and when they touch raw meat (OR=3.79 – 3.90; Figure 20).

Figure 19. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring campylobacteriosis associated to poor food handling practices

Figure 20. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring campylobacteriosis associated to food preparation practices

4. Conclusions

4.2 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic campylobacteriosis

- ❖ The outcomes from 71 case-control studies investigating routes of exposure for sporadic campylobacteriosis were meta-analysed, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ In children, the most important routes of transmission of campylobacteriosis are drinking untreated water (OR=4.93), contaminated or untreated drinking water (OR=4.939), consumption of raw-egg containing products (OR=4.85), exposure to recreational water (OR=4.68), exposure to farm/rural environment (OR=4.43) and person-to-person contagion (OR=4.22)
- ❖ Breastfed infants have on average 3.15 times lower odds of acquiring the disease than those who are not breastfed.
- ❖ The most important risk factors for transmission of campylobacteriosis in the mixed population are: handling of manure (OR=3.48), international travel (OR=3.05), occupational exposure to animals/carcasses/meat (OR=2.96) and recent use of anti-acids (OR=2.91)
- ❖ As a whole, the host-specific factors and some environmental/animal routes bear discernibly greater risk of transmission (pooled ORs from 2.06 – 3.48) than food consumption (pooled ORs from 0.75 to 1.78), except for raw milk at an OR of 2.64, and other meats comprising meat fondue, BBQ, grilled meat and offal at an OR of 2.21.
- ❖ Within the food vehicles of transmission, key determinants of disease in children are: raw milk (OR=3.05), pork (OR =2.34), other meats (OR=2.29), minced beef (OR=2.27), processed meats (OR=2.18), any composite food eaten out (OR=2.16) and poultry (OR=2.08)
- ❖ In the mixed population, the most important food routes of campylobacteriosis are: raw milk (OR=2.64), other meats (OR=2.21), poultry (OR=1.78), raw milk's cheese (OR=1.72), BBQ meats (OR=1.67), fast-food composite (OR=1.59) and raw seafood (OR=1.50).
- ❖ In both, the children and mixed population, drinking unpasteurised milk (ORs 3.05 and 2.64, respectively) bear greater risk of campylobacteriosis than consuming poultry meat (ORs 2.08 and 1.78, respectively).
- ❖ BBQ meats represent a significant source of campylobacteriosis (OR=1.67), likely to arise from reckless handling of raw and cooked meats and improper hygiene of BBQ utensils.

- ❖ People who stated having eaten undercooked chicken increase their odds of becoming infected with campylobacteriosis by 2.24 than those who *simply* recalled having eaten chicken.
- ❖ People who ate poultry, beef, processed meats and composite dishes prepared outside home had their odds of infection significantly increased by a factor of 1.251 – 1.850 whereas eating poultry prepared at home seemingly had a protective effect, by reducing the odds of acquiring campylobacteriosis by 1.270 (95% CI: 0.911 – 1.473).
- ❖ People who consumed raw milk and raw milk's cheese presented overall 2.42 times greater probability of becoming ill, whereas for those who consumed raw eggs and raw seafood, the mean base ORs increased by a lower factor of 1.89 and 1.62, respectively.
- ❖ Foodstuffs that on meta-analysis have weak or non-significant association with campylobacteriosis are: vegetables, fruits, molluscs, sprouts, dairy-based RTE, fungi and spices, fish, alcoholic beverages and processed fish.

5. References

5.2 Seventy-one case-control studies for *Campylobacter* spp

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2 Supplementary tables and figures for *Campylobacter* spp.

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of poultry (n=241)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.507	0.062		[0.385 – 0.630]	<.0001
Handl: Undercooked	0.805	0.086	28	[0.635 – 0.974]	<.0001
Setting: Eating out	0.325	0.055	63	[0.218 – 0.433]	<.0001
Setting: Home	-0.239	0.075	26	[-0.386 - -0.093]	0.001
Uni	-0.109	0.039		[-0.186 – 0.033]	0.005
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0951	QE(df=236)			
s^2 (residual)	0.2723	p<.001			
Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.827
Points removed	1				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of poultry. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S2. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of beef (n=50)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.323	0.165		[0.001 – 0.645]	0.050
Handl: Raw or undercook	0.632	0.177	8	[0.284 – 0.980]	<.0001
Setting: Eating out	0.511	0.191	12	[0.136 – 0.887]	0.008
Uni	-0.409	0.146		[-0.695 – 0.123]	0.005
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0686	QE(df=45)			
s^2 (residual)	1.3529	p=0.004			
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0001			0.027
Points removed	1				

Figure S2. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of poultry. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S3. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of eggs (n=14)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
MultiOR					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.895	0.410		[0.091 – 1.699]	0.030
Handl: Raw	0.638	0.378	4	[-0.103 – 1.378]	0.091
UniOR	-0.608	0.403		[-1.397 – 0.181]	0.131
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1196	QE(df=11)			
s^2 (residual)	0.3056	p=0.003			
Publication bias	0.0003	0.0004			0.5049
Points removed	0				

Figure S3. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of eggs

Table S4. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of seafood (n=20)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Handl & Setting: Base	-0.016	0.071		[-0.156 – 0.123]	0.816
Handl: Raw	0.485	0.125	9	[0.238 – 0.732]	<.0001
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0084	QE(df=18)			
s^2 (residual)	0.1033	p=0.370			
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.187
Points removed	0				

Figure S4. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of pork meat

Table S5. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of milk and cheese (n=46)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Handl: Base	-0.020	0.184	9	[-0.380 – 0.339]	0.912
Handl: Raw	0.884	0.203	37	[0.485 – 1.283]	<.0001
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2122	QE(df=44)			
s^2 (residual)	0.4738	p<.0001			
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.120
Points removed	0				

Figure S5. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of milk and cheese. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S6. Meta-analysis of the effects of setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of composite dishes (n=44)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Setting: Base	0.079	0.161	12	[-0.237 – 0.396]	0.622
Setting: Eating out	0.224	0.170	32	[-0.109 – 0.557]	0.187
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0517	QE(df=41)			
s^2 (residual)	0.3024	p<.0001			
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.013
Points removed	1				

Figure S6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of composite dishes. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S7. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of processed meat (n=65)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
MultiOR					
Setting: Base	0.304	0.099	54	[0.110 – 0.498]	0.002
Setting: Eating Out	0.615	0.159	11	[0.303 – 0.926]	<.0001
UniOR	-0.180	0.084		[-0.344 – -0.016]	0.032
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0541	QE(df=62)			
s^2 (residual)	0.2265	p<0.0001			
Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.4190
Points removed	0				

Figure S7. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of campylobacteriosis by consumption of eggs